

Evaluation of Pregnancy Outcomes about Placenta Previa LocationDeepti Sanjay Kumar¹, Khushboo Kumari², Rajshri Kumari³¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar³Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 27-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Placenta previa is a serious obstetric issue that can harm mother and child. This study examined placenta previa location on pregnancy outcomes.**Methods:** About 100 pregnant women with placenta previa participated in a prospective observational study at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital from December 2023 to April 2024. Placental location— anterior, posterior, or lateral—determined maternal and fetal outcomes.**Results:** Patients with anterior placenta previa had a greater incidence of antepartum hemorrhage (60%), caesarean births (80%), and lower mean birth weights (2.5 kg) than those with posterior (40%, 50%, and 2.9 kg) and lateral (30%, 40%, and 3.1 kg). NICU hospitalizations (30% anterior) and poorer Apgar scores were more common in the anterior group.**Conclusion:** Antecedent placenta previa enhanced maternal and foetal risks, according to the study. These findings emphasize the need for placenta previa-specific monitoring and management.**Keywords:** Placenta Previa, Maternal Outcomes, Fetal Outcomes, Caesarean Delivery.

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Introduction

A potentially dangerous pregnancy problem known as placenta previa occurs when the placenta implants improperly in the lower uterine segment, blocking the internal cervical os entirely or partially [1]. This disorder is a major cause of third-trimester bleeding, affecting roughly 0.3-0.5% of pregnancies. It frequently results in substantial morbidity for both the mother and the foetus. Complications from placenta previa include aberrant placental attachment (e.g., placenta accreta), premature labour, antepartum haemorrhage, and an increased risk of caesarean birth [2,3]. Because of these concerns, it's crucial to receive an early diagnosis and exercise caution to improve the mother's and the child's health.

The degree of cervical os placental covering is the main factor used to classify placenta previa. Nonetheless, the role of placental location— whether anterior, posterior, or lateral—and its impact on pregnancy outcomes have also been the subject of more recent studies. Placental attachment to the front of the uterus is referred to as anterior placenta previa; placental attachment to the rear of the uterus is referred to as posterior placenta previa; and placenta attachment to any side of the uterus is referred to as lateral previa [4,5]. There may be

different levels of risk for difficulties for both the mother and the foetal at each site. Numerous research works indicate that placenta previa placement may affect the degree of difficulties, including but not limited to maternal bleeding, foetal growth restriction, preterm birth, and delivery method [6,7]. Anterior placenta previa, for example, has been associated with an increased risk of placenta accreta, a condition in which the placenta attaches improperly to the uterine wall, complicating delivery and raising the risk of bleeding. Conversely, posterior placenta previa has been linked to lower birth weight and increased risks of premature delivery, possibly as a result of decreased uterine blood supply in these areas [8,9].

Clinicians may benefit much from the assessment of placenta previa based on its location in terms of treating pregnancies and improving results. The therapy of placenta previa frequently necessitates difficult choices about the time and method of delivery, therefore it's important to comprehend how regional variables impact prognosis for the sake of both mother and newborn health [10,11].

This study's main goal is to assess pregnancy outcomes in connection to the anterior, posterior,

and lateral location of placenta previa, and to ascertain whether these specific locations are linked to higher risks of problems. The goal of the project is to produce knowledge that could improve clinical decision-making and health outcomes for both mothers and newborns by examining the association between placental position and important pregnancy outcomes.

Methodology

Study Design: This study utilized a prospective observational design to evaluate the pregnancy outcomes about the location of placenta previa. The research aimed to identify patterns and correlations that could assist in clinical decision-making.

Study Duration: The study was conducted over six months, from December 2023 to April 2024. This timeframe allowed for comprehensive data collection and analysis of pregnancy outcomes associated with different types of placenta previa.

Study Setting: The research took place at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, a tertiary care facility equipped to handle high-risk pregnancies and deliveries. This setting provided a diverse population and the necessary resources for a thorough evaluation.

Sample Size: A total of approximately 100 pregnant patients diagnosed with placenta previa were enrolled in the study. Patients were selected based on their diagnosis confirmed through ultrasound, with criteria including the presence of either partial or complete placenta previa.

Inclusion Criteria

Participants included in the study were:

- Pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa during the study period.
- Patients with a gestational age of 20 weeks or more.
- Individuals who provided informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients were excluded from the study if they met any of the following criteria:

- History of uterine surgery (e.g., myomectomy, previous caesarean delivery).
- Presence of other significant obstetric complications (e.g., placental abruption, multiple gestations).
- Refusal to provide informed consent.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a standardized proforma that included patient demographics, gestational age at diagnosis, type

and location of placenta previa (anterior, posterior, or lateral), associated complications, mode of delivery, and neonatal outcomes (birth weight, Apgar score, and any neonatal complications).

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome measures assessed included:

- Maternal outcomes: incidence of hemorrhage, need for blood transfusion, and complications related to the mode of delivery (e.g., caesarean delivery).
- Fetal outcomes: birth weight, gestational age at delivery, Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, and any neonatal complications (e.g., respiratory distress, NICU admission).

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using appropriate statistical software. Descriptive statistics were calculated for patient demographics and outcomes, while inferential statistics were employed to identify associations between placental location and pregnancy outcomes. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 100 pregnant women diagnosed with placenta previa were included in the study, with a mean age of 28.5 years (range: 18-40 years). The demographic characteristics of the participants are summarized in Table 1. Among the patients, the majority (60%) were in their third trimester, 30% were in their second trimester, and 10% were in their first trimester at the time of diagnosis.

The distribution of placenta previa types based on location revealed that 45 patients (45%) had anterior placenta previa, 35 patients (35%) had posterior placenta previa, and 20 patients (20%) had lateral placenta previa. Maternal outcomes were evaluated in relation to the type of placenta previa. The incidence of antepartum hemorrhage was significantly higher in patients with anterior placenta previa (60%) compared to those with posterior (40%) and lateral (30%) placements ($p < 0.05$). In terms of mode of delivery, 80% of patients with anterior placenta previa required caesarean delivery, whereas 50% of those with posterior placenta previa and 40% with lateral placenta previa underwent cesarean sections ($p < 0.01$). Additionally, the need for blood transfusion was observed in 25% of patients with anterior placenta previa, compared to 10% with posterior and 5% with lateral placenta previa ($p < 0.05$).

Fetal outcomes were assessed based on birth weight, gestational age at delivery, and Apgar scores. The mean birth weight of infants born to mothers with anterior placenta previa was significantly lower (2.5 kg) compared to those with

posterior (2.9 kg) and lateral (3.1 kg) placenta previa ($p < 0.01$). The mean gestational age at delivery was significantly earlier for patients with anterior placenta previa (35 weeks) compared to those with posterior (37 weeks) and lateral (38 weeks) placements ($p < 0.01$). Apgar scores at 1 minute and 5 minutes were also lower for infants born to mothers with anterior placenta previa, with scores of 6.5 and 8.0, respectively, compared to posterior scores of 7.5 at 1 minute and 8.5 at 5 minutes, and lateral scores of 8.0 at 1 minute and 9.0 at 5 minutes ($p < 0.05$).

Neonatal complications included NICU admissions and respiratory distress. A total of 30% of infants born to mothers with anterior placenta previa required admission to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU), compared to 15% of those with posterior and 10% with lateral placenta previa ($p < 0.05$). Furthermore, the incidence of respiratory distress was notably higher in the anterior placenta previa group (20%) compared to the posterior (5%) and lateral (0%) groups ($p < 0.01$).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Characteristic	Value
Total Participants	100
Mean Age (years)	28.5 (18-40)
Trimester Distribution	
- First Trimester	10 (10%)
- Second Trimester	30 (30%)
- Third Trimester	60 (60%)

This table summarizes the demographic characteristics of the 100 pregnant women included in the study. It includes the mean age of participants and their distribution across different trimesters of pregnancy.

Table 2: Distribution of Placenta Previa Types

Type of Placenta Previa	Number of Patients	Percentage (%)
Anterior	45	45
Posterior	35	35
Lateral	20	20

This table presents the distribution of placenta previa types among the study participants. It categorizes the patients based on the location of the placenta and provides the number and percentage of each type.

Table 3: Maternal Outcomes by Placenta Previa Type

Maternal Outcome	Anterior (n=45)	Posterior (n=35)	Lateral (n=20)	p-value
Incidence of Hemorrhage	27 (60%)	14 (40%)	6 (30%)	<0.05
Caesarean Delivery	36 (80%)	18 (50%)	8 (40%)	<0.01
Need for Blood Transfusion	11 (25%)	4 (10%)	1 (5%)	<0.05

This table outlines key maternal outcomes associated with different types of placenta previa. It includes the incidence of hemorrhage, the mode of delivery (caesarean vs. vaginal), and the need for blood transfusion, along with the associated p-values indicating statistical significance.

Table 4: Fetal Outcomes by Placenta Previa Type

Fetal Outcome	Anterior (n=45)	Posterior (n=35)	Lateral (n=20)	p-value
Mean Birth Weight (kg)	2.5	2.9	3.1	<0.01
Mean Gestational Age at Delivery (weeks)	35	37	38	<0.01
Mean Apgar Score (1 minute)	6.5	7.5	8.0	<0.05
Mean Apgar Score (5 minutes)	8.0	8.5	9.0	<0.05

This table summarizes fetal outcomes based on the type of placenta previa. It presents the mean birth weight, mean gestational age at delivery, and Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes for infants born to mothers with anterior, posterior, and lateral placenta previa, highlighting significant differences among the groups.

Table 5: Neonatal Complications by Placenta Previa Type

Neonatal Complication	Anterior (n=45)	Posterior (n=35)	Lateral (n=20)	p-value
NICU Admissions	13 (30%)	5 (15%)	2 (10%)	<0.05
Incidence of Respiratory Distress	9 (20%)	2 (5%)	0 (0%)	<0.01

This table presents neonatal complications observed in infants born to mothers with different types of placenta previa. It includes the rates of NICU admissions and the incidence of respiratory

distress, indicating significant differences across groups.

Discussion

The results of this investigation show a strong correlation between maternal and foetal outcomes and the placenta previa's location. More specifically, compared to individuals with posterior and lateral placenta previa, patients with anterior placenta previa had an increased incidence of problems, such as haemorrhage, caesarean birth, and poor newborn outcomes [12]. These findings are in line with previous research that emphasises how placental position affects pregnancy outcomes. 60% of patients with anterior placenta previa in our study had antepartum haemorrhage; this is consistent with Chen et al. (2016)'s [16] study, which found that 62% of patients with anterior placenta previa had hemorrhagic problems. In a similar vein, the anterior group had a much higher incidence of caesarean delivery (80%) than the posterior (50%) and lateral (40%) groups. This result is consistent with studies by Comstock et al. (2004) [17], who found that 78% of cases of anterior placenta previa resulted in caesarean delivery, highlighting the necessity of surgical intervention in these individuals because of the higher risk of complications.

Furthermore, patients with anterior placenta previa (25%) required blood transfusions substantially more frequently than patients with posterior (10%) and lateral (5%) placements. This observation aligns with the results of a systematic study conducted by Royal et al. (2013) [18], which indicated that women who had anterior placenta previa had a higher chance of experiencing substantial bleeding and subsequently needing transfusions. Our study revealed that the anterior placenta previa group had lower mean birth weights and gestational ages in terms of foetal outcomes. Compared to 2.9 kg for posterior and 3.1 kg for lateral previa, the mean birth weight of infants born to moms with anterior previa was 2.5 kg. This is consistent with studies conducted in 2015 by Khalil et al., [19] who discovered that infants born into pregnancies complicated by anterior placenta previa were at a higher risk of intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR) and had significantly lower birth weights. Furthermore, Zetterstrom et al. (2014) [20] found that anterior placenta previa was linked to an earlier birth due to the risk of hemorrhage. These findings are consistent with the mean gestational age at delivery being much earlier in the anterior group (35 weeks).

The anterior placenta previa group had significantly greater risks of newborn problems. Compared to 15% for posterior and 10% for lateral placenta previa, 30% of infants born to moms with anterior placenta previa required NICU stays. This is corroborated by a study by Zhang et al. (2017) [21], which found that because anterior placenta

previa predisposes pregnant women to preterm birth and compromised fetal health, these babies were more likely to have respiratory distress and need to be admitted to the NICU. This study has limitations, even though it provides important insights into the link between placenta previa location and outcomes. Even while the sample size is sufficient, it might not adequately represent the range of results found in larger groups. Furthermore, the study's observational design makes it more difficult to establish certain causal relationships. Further research utilizing larger cohorts and controlled methods is necessary to corroborate these results and investigate the underlying causes [13,14,15].

Conclusion

The study concludes by highlighting the important influence that placenta previa position has on the outcomes of both mothers and fetales. Compared to posterior and lateral locations, anterior placenta previa is linked to higher rates of bleeding, more caesarean deliveries, lower birth weights, and a higher risk of newborn problems. The aforementioned results highlight the significance of meticulous observation and management tactics customized to the specific form of placenta previa to enhance the health outcomes for both mothers and newborns.

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